

Female Teachers Job Satisfaction and Working Conditions at Boys Primary School

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Abstract

Teachers should be encouraged by the higher authorities through incentives and reasonable pay packages. In this respect, facilities should be provided by the government. The objective of the study was; to find out female teachers' job satisfaction towards working condition at their institution. The study was descriptive in nature. The simple random technique was used to select respondents from the population and a sample of 335 were selected from district Sialkot. A survey questionnaire was used to collect data. After collection of data through questionnaire, it was analyzed using simple descriptive analysis and sparkline technique. The study found that female teachers have inconsistent responses, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree to the statement, "It is not easy for female teachers to visit the office of a male head on their own." While it is also found that female teachers appreciate the attitude of their head teachers. The study concluded that working conditions at the primary level need to be improved for female teachers to work efficiently. The study concluded that head teachers' professional attitude improves female teachers' ways of working and their outlook toward professionalism.

Keywords: Female Teacher, Job Satisfaction, Working Conditions

1. Introduction

An individual's emotional attachment to his work is called "job satisfaction," in other words, whether he likes the job or the features of the job, such as the nature of the work. These feelings can positively or negatively affect one's roles and responsibilities at the workplace. Job satisfaction illustrates how a human being is a content with his work. A happier worker is said to be satisfied and pleased with his field of work. Satisfaction is an emotional state in which he feels or thinks about his work. When a worker mentally feels happiness, ultimately, his performance increases (Chen, 2010).

"Career pride" is the attitude of an employee. If an employee's approach to his job is positive, he is satisfied. An employee is satisfied if his attitude towards the job is positive. Satisfaction is a state of mind that includes all characteristics of the employee's environment (Weiss, 2002). Working conditions and environmental facilities have a great effect on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is the fulfillment of the needs of an employee at his workplace. Better working conditions and the environment will satisfy the employee and can increase his efficiency; when employees are satisfied with the working environment, their output increases, decreasing the leaving rate of employees in an organization (Wilson, 2018).

Teachers should be encouraged by the higher authorities through incentives and reasonable pay packages. In this respect, facilities should be provided by the government. There are general feelings in Pakistan that teachers are dissatisfied with their jobs concerning salary and job security. In the profession of teaching, job satisfaction is vital. A satisfied teacher teaches his students effectively. As a result, the quality of education is improved (Chaudhry, Maqbool, Mushtaq, & Khan, 2013). Many factors exist that have a great influence on job satisfaction. They are linked to each other. If even a single factor is missed, that will create a sense of dissatisfaction. Teachers need more autonomy in performing co-curricular activities. He had no opportunity to take part in the decision-making process. It leads to the dissatisfaction of teachers. A dissatisfied teacher may decide to transfer to another school. Teachers with job autonomy show higher satisfaction levels than teachers who feel they have less autonomy. Headteacher support, student behavior, and peer relationships are associated with teachers' job satisfaction (Sharma & Jyoti, 2009).

The perception of job satisfaction differs from a gender perspective. Most female teachers willingly enter this profession. While only a few males join the teaching profession, many are still looking for an opportunity for another job. According to female teachers, job satisfaction is related to the nature of the job and the working environment. Job satisfaction requires a decent physical environment and harmonious social relations among colleagues. They also express that working under a democratic head teacher leads to job satisfaction. Tasnim (2006) described how most male teachers think job satisfaction means having a job and gaining status and prestige. A teacher is a designer of children's personalities. The teaching profession is ideal for women. The female teacher works with devotion. Female teachers educate citizens who benefit the country and the nation. These students will take part in the progress of the country. A satisfied female teacher always encourages the students. An educated woman plays the role of a nation-builder. For development, women's education is compulsory (Tasnim, 2006). Intrinsic and extrinsic rewards have a great influence on the job satisfaction of teachers. The reward is important for any business, organization, or school institution. It is very beneficial for the teacher's performance. It is a natural phenomenon that human performance is based on incentives and motivation. So, Ibrar and Khan (2015) found that teachers' overall performance in schools stayed high because they were motivated.

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There is a strong and positive link between the work environment and how happy teachers are with their jobs. It has been proven that the relationship between educational administration and teachers has a greater impact on the teachers' job satisfaction. Governmental policies and the autonomy of teachers' jobs also considerably influence teachers' job satisfaction. The interpersonal relationship among teachers negatively affects teachers' job satisfaction. Flexibility in working conditions has a significant impact on job satisfaction.

For the teaching profession, satisfaction is necessary. A satisfied teacher is a great advantage for learners. Motivated female teachers' level of job satisfaction is higher than male teachers' regarding working conditions and interpersonal relations. Favorable working conditions, management behavior, and colleague relations positively impact employee attitudes. Teachers have shown their highest level of job satisfaction over the intrinsic elements of job life, followed by interpersonal relations, management mindset, physical facilities, and working conditions. The major recommendations were to increase the benefits and incentives and enhance the school's physical facilities. Better cooperation by the head teacher affects the mindset of his subordinates. Employees are satisfied if the behavior is declarative (Sharma & Jyoti, 2006).

Female education is important for the economic development activities of the country. Female teachers appointed to boys' schools are teaching male students. Female teachers easily understand the psychology of primary-level children. Primary and elementary boys' schools have both male and female teachers. Teaching females in a boy's school is a new experiment for the government and female teachers. The class discipline of female teachers remained poor among male students. They have difficulties making eye contact with male elementary school students approaching puberty. There may exist examples of sexual harassment on either side of the teaching and learning process (Awan & Riasat, 2015).

Pakistan is a developing country. Pakistan participates actively in the organization Education for All (EFA). Women are 48.6% of the total population. For developing countries, empowering women is very important. Since 2005, female teachers have been recruited in boys' government schools in Punjab. Highly qualified teachers were recruited in the school education department of Punjab.

According to the education department's contract policy, women can also apply for positions as elementary school teachers and senior elementary school teachers in schools for boys. In the appointment conditions for educators, it is mentioned that if a male and female candidate obtain the same merit, the female candidate will be preferred. This project was started to give women in the education department more power to meet the millennium development goals (Punjab School Education Department, 2018). The working conditions of female teachers performing their duties in boys' schools differ from those in girls' schools. In boys' schools, the head teacher is male; in girls' schools, the head teacher is female. In the present situation in male schools, males and females work together. Female teachers feel better with colleagues of the same gender.

1.1. Research Objectives

- To find out female teachers' job satisfaction towards working condition at their institution.

2. Review of Related Literature

Staff job satisfaction is a key indicator of successful schools. Satisfied teachers boost performance. Female teachers have equal job satisfaction. Women teachers are polite and pay more attention to primary students. Female teachers understand junior students' psychology, habits, and needs. Motherly love makes women better elementary school teachers. Female teachers can improve educational policies and human growth. Feminine educators are revered for their contributions to society. Teachers' job satisfaction affects their performance. Smart people are satisfied with their great jobs. A happy worker respects his noble profession. The right attitude for long-term employees is job satisfaction. Employer-worker satisfaction is crucial. One person values his job-related creativity.

Job satisfaction is linked to experienced staff recruitment and cultural retention. He evaluates his workplace based on his daily experiences. He could contrast what is with what he desires from that organization. Thus, it refers to the employee's work history and reward preferences. Psychology studies workplace behavior (Lu, Barriball, Zhang, & While, 2012).

It is an emotional response to multiple facts. Employment satisfaction is no longer a single, all-encompassing idea. A person can be very happy with one part of their job but not with others. Leadership affects job design, satisfaction, and other psychological issues. "Job satisfaction can be viewed as an international feeling about the job; job pleasure is interconnected with worker needs," says Spector. Employees are paid. Is his pay enough? (Spector, 1997).

Three job satisfaction frameworks dominate the scientific literature. The content hypothesis states that job satisfaction occurs when an individual's employment meets their need for self-actualization and development. Process theory, the second abstract framework, examines how well excellent employment meets expectations and values to explain job happiness. Situational theories, which state that "work pleasure is a function of how successfully an individual's features interact or come together with organizational characteristics," are the third abstract group.

Human motivation theories influence career advancement perceptions. Maslow's needs hierarchy theory, Herzberg's motivator-hygiene theory, the Job Characteristics Model, the dispositional approach, and the

Expectancy theory are prominent in this field. Maslow's needs hierarchy theory (1943) was one of the first to study job satisfaction. The theory proposes five levels of human wishes.

This notion states that workers' physiological needs—air, food, water, and health—must be met first. The first level addresses body necessities, and these are vital. Without these essential demands, how can a worker be happy? Individuals progress to the second level after satisfying their first-level needs. Safety and satisfaction are mandatory in the second level. Safety refers to workplace conditions. He needs safety gear and a uniform at work. Security means job and workplace accident protection. Job security ensures that the company will provide for him if he has an accident. War and other unfavorable conditions necessitate worker safety. Workers want protection from job loss and illness (Ramlall, 2004).

Researchers believe the final stage of self-actualization cannot be measured. Respecting this level is difficult. The wearer did not feel it yet. Safety and respect were not his goals. During self-actualization, he worked passionately. Abdul Sitar Edhi from Pakistan fits the bill. He improved people's lives. He self-actualized in his work. His passion satisfied him. Despite living in poverty, many poets, scientists, and writers achieved self-actualization. Self-actualized people are moral. Herzberg's motivator-hygiene theory is also known as the "two-factor theory." Hygiene factors improve staff satisfaction. Workers are affected by these factors. These indicators indicate employee satisfaction.

The staff is dissatisfied; the pay comes first, whereas salary boosts worker happiness. A worker feels entitled to a fair wage. A worker with a good salary should have used the organization's resources to get a higher-paying job (Suleman and Hussain, 2018).

Figure 2 Representation of Herzberg's theory

It was argued that an organization develops a work environment that can utilize its workers' abilities efficiently. The organization enhances its workers' ability to increase the organization's profit. If a worker has been assigned a challenging task, he feels pleasure in an organization. It was also said that employee-to-employee interactions and good working relationships are very important to job satisfaction. Working conditions include working hours, job safety, necessary needs, interpersonal relations among the employees, and the influence of decisions made by the supreme authority. According to Herzberg's theory, these are dissatisfiers. Positive hygiene factors result in job satisfaction through worker loyalty, efficiency, and commitment (Chandrasekar, 2011).

Satisfaction is a collection of emotions and behaviors associated with one's job. Philosophy is founded on the famous Maslow's Needs Theory. Some factors satisfy the employee, and some provide dissatisfaction. Workers are driven by their achievements, the work itself, recognition, and the chance to move up in the company (Herzberg, 1987). Objections are raised on two-factor theories as they are held with weak methodology (Mira, Aya, & Hamzeh, 2015). It resulted in alternative efforts to test the theory, which had mixed results. Those are supported by some researchers (Schmidt, 2006).

3. Model of Job Characteristics

There are five dimensions in this model. First is expertise diversity—the extent to which workers perform different activities. The worker learns different skills at the workplace. The worker feels satisfaction in performing challenging duties. The researcher focused on what job conditions create motivation which leads to job satisfaction. The fundamental concept of this theory is based on three types of relationships. The first relationship

is between effort and performance. The highest level of effort will result in a high level of performance. The second type of relationship is between performance and reward. A worker with the best performance receives a better salary and bonus rewards. The third type of relationship is between reward and personal goal. When a worker gets a reward from the organization, he fulfills his desires in life (Muneer, 2003).

Figure 3 Job Characteristics Model

It was discovered that an employee feels satisfied when performing various difficult tasks. He feels pride in the completion of the task. Employee tasks are important for the development of an organization, its workers, and customer satisfaction. He has been empowered to choose the task. The worker's job autonomy leads to creativity in the work style. He can schedule his task. He manages his procedure. He performs the duty with responsibility. This idea is work design (Roberts & Glick, 2008). Their connection to the organization determines employee job satisfaction. If a teacher feels that the teaching profession suits him, he is comfortable. As a result, he performs better at his institution. One of the main reasons for the continuous decline in the quality of education in our country is teacher dissatisfaction regarding their jobs (Ahmad & Akbar, 2010).

Teacher job satisfaction is directly correlated with age and intrinsic factors. Student characteristics play a vital role in a teacher's satisfaction. Students' behavior inside the classroom and outside co-curricular activities also affects the teacher's psychological satisfaction. Positive student-teacher interactions in mixed-gender environments increase the level of satisfaction. Chen looked into how happy Chinese elementary school teachers were with their jobs and found that they were generally unhappy. He found that young, less experienced, and junior teachers are more satisfied than senior teachers. He also observed that the needs of young teachers are less than those of senior teachers. Senior teachers are unsatisfied due to working teachers' governance and promotion policies. Work conditions, leadership style, and future career planning contribute to their satisfaction. Smith (2007) says that working conditions greatly impact how happy teachers are in all types of schools.

Job satisfaction is a dependent variable, and work conditions, relationships with coworkers, facilities at work, and achievements are independent variables. The independent variable condition can motivate the teacher. The teacher will be more satisfied if the job is attractive. A satisfied teacher will work with devotion, and resultantly high outcomes exist. Interpersonal relations are very effective for the satisfaction of the teacher. Teachers' relations with peers should be participative. All teachers should help each other to facilitate. The head teacher makes decisions after consulting with colleagues. The school building must be in a safe environment. The atmosphere of the school must be healthy. Transport should be available for teachers. The people of the community must be cooperative (Wilson, 2018).

A study has found that the job satisfaction of male and female educators who work in mixed-gender environments changes significantly. Male head teachers have found it difficult to handle issues regarding female staff, parents, and students. Male teachers feel awkward being supervised by female officers. On the other hand, it has been said that female teachers are silenced in schools for boys because their ideas are not given much weight in official meetings. Mocheche, Bosire, and Raburu (2017) say that male teachers have given themselves the upper hand in school management meetings, which is frustrating for female teachers.

Female teachers who work in classrooms with both male and female teachers have said they feel respected, helpful, professional, and able to work with male teachers. Their relationship with male colleagues has remained positive. A similar study of how happy female and male teachers are with their jobs found that male teachers are happier than female teachers. In other cases, researchers discovered that female educators are more pleased than male instructors. The study of how happy Chinese women were with their jobs found that many male and female jobs were the same. Women feel their jobs are inferior to men's, making them less satisfied (Luo, 2016). Women are likely to be more satisfied and happier than men. Women feel happy about earning money. They fulfill their economic needs (Clark, 1997).

The study's findings demonstrated a link between organizational commitment and work satisfaction. The employee's confidence in fairness governing policies was more satisfied and committed. Committed employees feel S relations with the organization, and the organization considers them fit for the job. Employees feel that justice in an organization is secure and satisfactory (Kamran & Rehman, 2012). Working conditions, such as governing policies, school schedules, working hours, and environmental amenities, significantly impact teacher satisfaction. Teachers are retained if they are pleased with the school's working conditions (Naz, 2017).

4. Research Methodology

Cresswell (2014) says that a quantitative approach is one in which the researcher uses claims from positivism to learn more. The research was descriptive, and the data was quantitative. In the district of Sialkot, 16,755 female teachers are working in government elementary schools (Punjab Schools Education Department, 2022). A simple random sampling method was used to choose 335 female elementary school teachers from District Sialkot, which is 20% of the total population.

For the study, Akhtar (2022) used a 36-item questionnaire with three main categories: school environment, working conditions, and relationships with other people. However, for the current study, the researchers used the questionnaire items related to the working conditions, which were nine (9) in number. These items were constructed for collecting data on a five-point Likert scale, i.e., "strongly agree," "agree," "undecided, disagree, and "strongly disagree" (Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2011). The overall reliability of the questionnaire was 0.881 coefficient alpha.

Using the tool mentioned above to get information from the people being studied, the researcher went to the sample teachers and gave them the questionnaire in person. They were fully informed about the questionnaire completion process. The researcher chose to go in a circle. One tehsil was allotted two full days. The daytrip began in Tehsil Daska. One of the researchers, a native of the tehsil, made it simple to contact the teachers. The researchers then traveled to Tehsil Pasrur, Sialkot, and Sambrial. The researchers appreciated each sample participant for their significant input and time.

In 1986, Kerlinger defined "data analysis" as "categorizing, manipulating, and summarizing data to obtain the answer to the research question." The collected data was put into MS Excel, and the frequency and sparkline for each item were found.

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of working condition

Items	SA	A	U	DA	SDA	Sparkline
WC01	13	37	14	137	134	
WC02	64	78	56	59	78	
WC03	70	64	67	60	74	
WC04	71	56	76	69	63	
WC05	68	64	66	72	65	
WC06	74	67	66	51	77	
WC07	71	75	70	62	57	
WC08	80	63	68	61	63	
WC09	69	77	45	74	70	

Table 1 depicts respondents' responses toward the statements related to the female teachers' job satisfaction toward the prevailing working conditions in elementary schools in district Sialkot. The data was interpreted through frequency and Sparkline. In response of the statement, "When compared to other educators, I have a similar number of periods" majority of the respondents (137 + 134 = 271) disagree. Majority of the respondents (64 + 78 = 142) responded that the head teacher did not consider gender equality. Female teachers equally responded against the statement, "It's not easy for a female educator to visit the office of a male head on her alone". While the majority of female teachers disagreed to the statement, "Casual leaves are available to me whenever I need them". The respondents (72 + 65 = 137) responded that they did not feel fortunate to be a teacher at this institution. The female teachers (74 + 67 = 141) agreed that job satisfaction can be raised by financial rewards such as higher pay or bonuses. Majority of the female teachers (71 + 75 = 146) agreed that they appreciate the friendly attitude of their head teacher. Majority of the female teachers (80 + 63 = 143) enjoy their summer vacations. Female teachers (74 + 70 = 144) disagreed to the statement, "Teachers have easy access to medical and maternity leaves".

6. Findings and Discussion

The study looks at how happy female teachers are with their jobs and what the working conditions are like at primary schools for boys. The study results showed that female teachers are unhappy with how the primary school

schedule is set up, while most teachers said that their head teacher did not care about gender equality in their school. By looking at the primary data, Chaudhry and Rehman (2009) used Legit regression analysis to examine the gender discrepancy in education and its effects on rural poverty in Pakistan. It showed that gender inequality in the education system negatively affects poverty in rural areas. The study found that female teachers have inconsistent responses, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree to the statement, "It is not easy for female teachers to visit the office of a male head on their own." Flexibility in working conditions has a significant impact on job satisfaction. Suitable working conditions encourage and motivate a school teacher. It is essential to create a relaxed and safe atmosphere (Muhammad & Ahmed, 2015). It is also very hard to take casual or medical leaves from school. It was found that female teachers did not feel comfortable working at boys' primary schools due to the working conditions at the primary level. Working conditions, such as governing policies, school schedules, working hours, and environmental amenities, significantly impact teacher satisfaction. Teachers are retained if they are pleased with the school's working conditions (Naz, 2017). Most female teachers agreed that bonuses and other financial benefits make them happier at work.

On the other hand, female teachers appreciate the attitude of their head teachers. Better cooperation by the head teacher affects the mindset of his subordinates. Employees are satisfied if the behavior is declarative (Sharma & Jyoti, 2006). Furthermore, teachers enjoy summer vacations at the primary level every year. In the end, female teachers found hardships in getting their medical or maternity leave.

7. Conclusion

The study concluded that female teachers are happy with how the heads of primary schools treat them as a whole, but they have some doubts about the administrative level because the working conditions at the primary school level could be better. Female teachers feel discrimination in the distribution of academic work and other administrative issues. On the contrary, they were satisfied with the cooperative and friendly attitude of the head teachers at primary school levels. Overall, working conditions at the primary level need to be improved for female teachers to work efficiently. The study concluded that head teachers' professional attitude improves female teachers' ways of working and their outlook toward professionalism.

7.1. Recommendations

The conclusion of the study provide following recommendations;

1. Female teachers may provide with suitable working conditions in the boys primary school to get more efficiency in their work and for professional delicacy.
2. It may also be recommended that female teacher may provide the medical and maternity leave with ease by all ways and means.

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